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Engravings with Numerals on Roman Bronze
Coins and *Tesserae* from the 4th Century AD

by

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[PLATES 4–6]

Introduction

The following presents a group of Roman bronze coins issued during the fourth century AD, which were later repurposed by engraving a large-sized Roman numeral on their reverses. Similar engravings also occur on two Roman provincial coins of the principate as well as on a handful of Roman *tesserae* from the fourth century, which are presented here for completeness as they are relatable to the same conversion pattern and phenomenon.

It should be noted in advance that the incised coins and *tesserae* recorded here have been in museum or private collections since at least the nineteenth century (where known), or have recently surfaced on the market. Since their find-spots are unknown, dating and analysing the engravings cannot rely on any archaeological context data, and must by necessity be based on other methods. This paper aims to explore the reuse of these objects in the late Roman period through a comparative approach, and provides some thoughts on the purpose, context, and meaning of their uncommon numeral marks.

The contribution is divided into four parts: the first gives a presentation of the materials and summarises their *status quaestionis*; an identification of the coin series to which these pieces formerly belonged is proposed in the second part through analysis of the types displayed on their obverses; the third section deals with the numeral incisions on the reverses and identifies the specimens which form part of the same ensemble; finally, a possible affiliation of the numeral marks and their inherent purpose is suggested in the fourth part. A catalogue including all specimens available to date is provided at the end of the contribution.

The material: defining features and the state of the art

The material discussed here consists of fifteen Roman bronze coins (Cat. nos 1–15, **Pls 4–5, 1–15**), and five late Roman bronze and brass tokens (= ‘Vota Publica’ series) (Cat. nos 16–20, **Pl. 5, 16–20**). The original images on the reverse of all specimens were erased and replaced with a Roman numeral. This engraving was added at some point after the coin or token was in circulation, implying the acquisition of a new value or use which displaced the original purpose. An exception is the coin

labelled here as no. 13, which shows two engraved non-numeral symbols (a palm branch and the PE monogram). The inclusion of this exception will be explained later in the text.

Over the past forty years or more, the phenomenon of engraving and countermarking Greek and Roman coinage has attracted tremendous interest in scholarship and on the market, and has also been the subject of specialised numismatics websites.¹ For the countermarking Howgego's 1985 study provided the fundamental reference work for 'Greek imperial countermarks' occurring on Roman provincial coins from the late first century BC until the reign of Aurelian (AD 270–75), leading a large and growing bibliography on the matter.² Subsequent scholarship has expanded upon his work or explored other types of countermarks such as those found on Roman imperial coins (largely from the Julio–Claudian and Flavian periods), as well as on Roman medallions and contorniates.³ These studies have repeatedly highlighted how the re-use of coins was exceedingly complex in the ancient world and involved a variety of chronological and geographic domains.

The countermarking of coins marks a secondary, but equally informative phase in the life cycle of a coin. Especially for those cases where the repurposing or reintroduction of coins as currency by the State or a government authority can be ascertained, the practice of punching marks containing numbers, letters, symbols, or even a combination of these on coins was generally aimed at changing or confirming their value or 'denomination', to extend the geographical area in which they would be accepted as legal tender, or to allow their continued use in case they had been in circulation for a considerable period of time or were issued by a previous state or political authority. But, as noted by M.P. Theophilos, among others, 'countermarking the coins [...] not only served political purposes, but also saved great time and expense of minting new coins while still conveying an important message affirming the power and control to the inhabitants of the region'.⁴

Yet, while proper countermarks, counterstamps and punchmarks were typically public, official, and monetary, the wide array of incisions and other graffiti found on ancient coinage after their striking also displays that, when needed, coins were also reused by a non-public authority or for a non-monetary purpose. This suggests that numerous individuals each with their own potential intentions lay behind the broad phenomenon of coin re-use in antiquity, which makes it necessary to analyse

¹ For the latter, see for instance the 'Museum of Countermarks on Roman Coins' section from the *Roman Numismatic Gallery* website (<https://www.romancoins.info/Content.html>) or, for Roman provincial coins, the sub-section 'Countermarks' on the online version of the *Roman Provincial Coinage (RPC)* (<https://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/countermark>).

² Howgego 1985. E.g., see further Barag 1967; Rosenberg 1978; Barag and Qedar 1994; Martini 2003; van Heesch 2014; Martini 2017.

³ On the subject, the bibliography is enormous due to the diversity of countermarks on Roman coins and medallions and their different usage and period of application. For some of the countermarks on coins from the Julio–Claudian period until the early reign of Vespasian, see, for example: Kraay 1956; Martini 1980; Baker 1984; Martini 1999; Topalov 2002; Kemmers 2004; Martini 2006; May 2009; Werz 2009; Martini 2018; Martini 2021. For countermarks, graffiti, as well as holes found on Roman medallions and contorniates cf. Alföldi and Alföldi 1990, pp. 241–353; Holmes 2004; Mittag 1999, pp. 167–71; Mondello 2016; Mondello 2019.

⁴ Theophilos 2020, p. 90.

this evidence on a case by case basis. A countermark-oriented approach has also occasionally been followed in surveys dealing with Athenian tokens (*symbola*), *spintriae*, and Roman bronze and lead *tesserae* as well, although to a lesser extent due to the wider neglect that has long affected this class of materials in scholarship.⁵ Additional categories of countermarks and other interventions on Roman coins, medallions, and *tesserae* executed after their production still need to be fully investigated, having not found a precise place along the continuum of academic research.⁶

The case study examined here has been the subject of almost no discussion within modern scholarship. Some of these specimens were listed with countermarked Roman coins and tokens in a late nineteenth century publication, but were given no contextualisation of their own.⁷ Others have only been studied selectively, but without attempts to identify the relevant coin series or issuing authorities; more importantly, some of these pieces were incorrectly associated with certain late Roman Christian bronze *tesserae* dated to the reign of Honorius and Arcadius (c. AD 404–08), regarded as the ‘pagan counterpart’ of the latter as well as a ‘halb versteckte spielerische Manifestation der heidnischen Reaktion’.⁸ As a result, the known examples displaying these numeral engravings have not been examined together to date. The body of available material thus demands a new evaluation of these rare marks with Roman numerals. In addition to pieces recorded in earlier research, this paper includes some new specimens, either preserved in public collections or recently emerged on the market. The following sections will therefore focus first on the original obverse types of these pieces, then on the engraved Roman numerals on the reverse and their possible meaning.

Identification of the Roman coins and tesserae with numeral engravings

This section analyses the obverse types of the coins and *tesserae* under study that, unlike their reverse, were neither erased nor engraved with numeral marks. These permit the identification of some of the original components of the artefacts at the

⁵ For countermarks on the Athenian tokens (*symbola*), cf. Crosby 1964, p. 83; Gkikaki 2019, pp. 132–4; Mondello 2023, pp. 209–12, 223–25. For countermarks, holes, or ancient metal inlays applied to Roman bronze and lead tokens, cf. Mowat 1898; Alföldi 1964; Alföldi 1975; Perassi 2011, pp. 266–7; Mondello 2021, pp. 142–3; Rowan 2023, pp. 26–8. As for the *spintriae*, some of the pieces received private Renaissance silver-inlaid punch marks showing a tiny eagle, which have been regarded as marks of the Gonzaga family from Mantua or the House of Este, Dukes of Ferrara, Modena, and Reggio: Riva and Simonetta 1979; Riva and Simonetta 1983; Reggiani 1992; Campana 2009, pp. 44, 57. These Renaissance silver-inlaid punch marks also occur on some of the fourth-century AD ‘Vota Publica’ tokens: Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), nos E102.1, S58.3, I127.2.

⁶ For instance, some Roman coins and medallions on the market are clipped, with serrated or scalloped edges, or have a cross-shaped engraving on one or both sides of the flan, which were mostly described as solidus weights or gaming tokens: e.g. Auctiones GmbH, E-Auction 46, 27 March 2016, lot 71 (= Maximianus Herculius Æ medallion); CNG, E-Auction 527, 16 November 2022, lot 235 (= Elagabalus Roman provincial coin).

⁷ de Belfort 1892, pp. 129–32, and p. 171.

⁸ Alföldi 1975, p. 20. On the above-mentioned Christian bronze *tesserae*, which show reverse types referring to early Christian imagery of saints accompanied by a Roman numeral in the exergue or a mix of Latin letters and Roman numerals, cf. Mondello 2021.

time of their production through a comparison with regular official coins, such as their denominational value, the coin series to which they belonged, and their issuing authorities. The analysis provided here is based on the metrology and weights of each specimen, the engraving style of the obverse portrait, as well as on the obverse legend and its break. However, due to the poor condition of some of the pieces or the reoccurrence of the same individual style and imperial portrait type on multiple issues by the same mint – as well as the lack of the original reverse –, a secure identification of the relevant coin issue is not always possible. Nonetheless, combination of module, weight, stylistic, and epigraphic details at least permit a general chronology for their original production.

Catalogue no. 1 is from the reign of Nero (AD 54–68) (**Pl. 4, 1**). The coin was part of a provincial Roman issue struck in AD 66–7 by the mint of Corinth, Achaëa. The existing coins from this issue, made of leaded bronze with a consistent diameter of 20mm, show a radiate head of Nero to either right or left on the obverse, accompanied by the legend NERO CAE(SAR) AVG IMP (**Pl. 5, 21**).⁹ The obverse legend is poorly legible on catalogue no. 1 probably due to the poor preservation state of the piece rather than the result of a deliberate alteration. The original reverse type of this Corinthian coinage, which was erased on no. 1, bears a galley sailing left, with a legend mentioning Lucius Rutilius Pisus or Publius Memmius Cleander, *duovir* magistrates of AD 66–7, with ADVE AVG in field.¹⁰

Catalogue no. 2 is a provincial coin from the mint of Alabanda, Caria (**Pl. 4, 2**). This series, which has been dated to the reign of Vespasian (AD 69–79),¹¹ shows a bearded and draped head to right, identified as the Demos¹² or Zeus,¹³ with the legend ΑΛΑΒΑΝΔΕΩΝ. Both the obverse legend and type can be easily recognised on no. 2. As for the reverse type, the available coins from the Alabanda series display a motif depicting the Senate seated to the left, holding a lituus (?) and a scepter, with the legend CYNKAHTOC in right and left field (**Pl. 5, 22**), which is no longer visible on this piece.

The other engraved Roman bronze coins in the catalogue all come from the fourth century AD. Of these, the earliest coin was issued in the name of Maxentius (AD 306–12), and bears a laureate head right, with the legend IMP C MAXENTIVS P F AVG (Cat. no. 3, **Pl. 4, 3**). The Æ2 size of the coin, the imperial portrait type, imperial titulature and unbroken form of the obverse legend have close parallels with the *folles* produced by the mints of Rome and Ostia from AD 308 to 311–12. As shown by Sutherland, the Roman and Ostian mints shared much in both the choice and in the treatment of types;¹⁴ the absence of the reverse type on no. 3 thus makes it thus difficult to attribute the imperial portrait to a specific mint. The Maxentius portrait occurs in an exceedingly similar style in many Æ2 issues from both mints.

⁹ Cf. *RPC I*, no. 1204.

¹⁰ Some thirty specimens from this Roman provincial series of Corinth are available. Cf. *BMC 567*; Amandry 1988, pp. 217–19. See also the updated online version of *RPC I*, no. 1204: <https://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/coins/1/1204>.

¹¹ Forni 1954, p. 105, no. 150; *RPC II*, no. 1203.

¹² Thus *RPC II*, no. 1203 (<https://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/coins/2/1203>).

¹³ Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 6, pl. 7.6.

¹⁴ *RIC VI*, pp. 393–4.

However, according to this author, stylistic similarities make either the obverse dies from the CONSERV–VRB SVAE *folles* by the Roman mint (AD 308–310/11),¹⁵ or the AETERNITAS AVG N *folles* by the Ostian mint (AD 309–12),¹⁶ the most likely options for the series identification.

Another Æ2 specimen bears a pearl–diademed, draped, and cuirassed bust of Constantius II right, wearing a *paludamentum* on the obverse, with the legend D N CONSTAN–TIVS P F AVG (Cat. no. 4, **Pl. 4, 4**). The analysis of the facial features and bust details (in particular, the nose ending with a sharp angle turned down, the hair ending in locks on the neck, square shape of the drapery neckline), as well as the imperial legend and the coin size, connect this piece to either of the large ‘Fel Temp Reparatio’ Æ2s struck in AD 348–51 by the mint of Constantinople (**Pl. 5, 23**).¹⁷

A numeral incision on the reverse of a bronze coin issued in the name of the usurper Magnentius (AD 350–53) is portrayed in the drawing of a now–lost piece, which was once part of the collection of the renowned numismatist Auguste de Belfort (1824–1907), treasurer of the *Société Française de Numismatique* since 1869 and afterwards director of the *Annuaire de la Société Française de Numismatique*. The coin was described and illustrated by de Belfort in his 1892 publication in the *ASFN*, and was apparently still housed in his collection at that time (Cat. no. 5, **Pl. 4, 5**).¹⁸ The drawing shows a bare–headed, draped and cuirassed bust of Magnentius right, accompanied by the legend [D N] MAGNEN–TIVS P F AVG,¹⁹ with the letter A behind the bust in the left field. Sadly, the loss of the de Belfort specimen as well as the widespread use of this imperial portrait and the obverse legend on multiple coinages issued by a number of imperial mints active at the time of Magnentius (e.g. Amiens, Aquileia, Arles, Rome, Lyons) does not allow a more precise identification of the coin and its issuing mint.

Eight engraved Æ3 coins of Julian are in the catalogue. As indicated by the module and the portrait type showing the imperial bust on the left in military dress, these specimens match the ‘VOTA X – XX’ issues which were struck in the name of Julian by different imperial mints. These are reformed Æ3, with an average weight around 2.95g and diameter between 19 and 21mm, which were aimed at celebrating Julian’s anticipated *decennalia*, with production probably beginning sometime after his entry into Constantinople on 11 December 361.²⁰ The extremely worn state of

¹⁵ *RIC* VI, Rome, nos 208–13 (AD 308–10), 258, 263 (AD 310–11).

¹⁶ *RIC* VI, Ostia, nos 14 and 16 (AD 309), 35, 39, 41, 43 (AD 309–12). Unfortunately, no die–links between specimen no. 3 and available bronze coins of Maxentius have been identified by the author, despite several attempts.

¹⁷ *RIC* VIII, Constantinople, nos 81–2 (AD 348–51).

¹⁸ de Belfort 1892, p. 130, pl. V.4. This coin of Magnentius, whose date of acquisition in the de Belfort collection is not known, does not appear in the relevant collection sale catalogue: cf. Delestre and Hoffmann 1888. Accordingly, the coin was not part of the assemblage from de Belfort’s collection which was offered for sale in Paris from 20 to 25 February 1888.

¹⁹ The obverse legend, correctly transcribed in the description provided by de Belfort 1892, p. 130, appears instead without the titulus D N in the illustration of the piece. The latter clearly resulted from an error by the designer of the plate, as the imperial legend MAGNEN–TIVS P F AVG is otherwise unattested and not shown in surviving coinage.

²⁰ *RIC* VIII, pp. 53–4.

one of the coins, kept at the British Museum, unfortunately precludes any attempt at identification (Cat. no. 6, **Pl. 4, 6**). For the other pieces, comparison with Julian's *vota* coinages allow comment on their date and issuing location, based on the obverse legend and its break as well as some substantial variations that can be discerned in the execution of Julian's portrait by the imperial mints.

Two specimens (Cat. nos 8–9, **Pl. 4, 8–9**) were made from the VOT/X/MV•LT/XX series struck by the mint of Rome (AD 361–63) (**Pl. 5, 24**).²¹ The attribution of nos 8–9 to the Roman mint is supported by the treatment of Julian's long beard in individual, wavy stripes and his forward-leaning bust, which most differentiates Julian's Roman coin portrait from those of other mints.

One of the Julian pieces (Cat. no. 12, **Pl. 4, 12**) shows stylistic affinities with some of the obverse dies from the VOT/X/MVLT/XX issue by the mint of Constantinople (AD 361–63).²² These can be seen not only in the general engraving style of the mint of Constantinople, but also in the combination of certain details of the imperial portrait and its attributes, such as the large, elongated face of Julian, the depiction of the left armour epaulette in three large bands (which is generally portrayed differently or is even almost indiscernible on the *vota* coins of other mints), and the slice-shaped spearhead. Some similarities with the coins of Constantinople can also be found in the imperial portrait of specimen no. 7 (Cat. no. 7, **Pl. 4, 7**), but are insufficient for a secure attribution and this mint identification remains uncertain.²³

The remaining three Julian pieces belong to the Æ3 series VOT/X/MVLT/XX struck by the mint of Siscia (Cat. nos 10–11, 13, **Pls 4–5, 10–11, 13**),²⁴ as indicated by the short beard of the imperial effigy, with grape-shaped locks. Julian's head on specimens nos 10 and 13 has remarkable similarities with some of the obverse dies from *RIC* VIII, Siscia, no. 415 due to its small and pointy facial features, most notably the nose (**Pl. 6, 25**).

Two of the other engraved coins refer to the second Valentinian generation (AD 375–94). Piece no. 14 (**Pl. 5, 14**) is an Æ3 bearing a youthful, pearl-diademed, and cuirassed bust of Valentinian II right, wearing a *paludamentum*, with the legend D N VALENTINIA–NVS IVN P F AVG. The specimen can be confidently attributed to the mint of Aquileia. This is indicated by the imperial portrait type and its small size, but also by the obverse legend, its division, as well as its position in the field. Indeed, the obverse legend (divided–NVS) fully surrounds the imperial effigy of Valentinian II (a mostly distinctive feature of the Aquileia coinage) on piece no. 14, whereas the lower part of the imperial bust generally occupies the space between the beginning and the end of the legend on coins from other mints, as found in the coeval Æ3 issues of Antioch and Nicomedia. The metrological, typological, and epigraphic data leaves the only possible identification of the piece as either the 'Gloria Romanorum' (AD 375–78) or 'Securitas Rei Publicae' issues (AD 375–78)

²¹ *RIC* VIII, Rome, nos 328–30 (AD 361–63).

²² *RIC* VIII, Constantinople, nos 165–7 (AD 361–63).

²³ Conversely, the website of the BnF, where the pieces labelled here as no. 7 and 12 are housed, attributes these two coins to the Roman mint. See: <https://catalogue.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb45877358t> (= piece no. 7); <https://catalogue.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb45877360c.public> (= piece no. 12).

²⁴ *RIC* VIII, Siscia, nos 414–16, 420–2 (AD 361–63).

(**Pl. 6, 26**).²⁵ Number 15 (**Pl. 5, 15**) bears a pearl–diademed and cuirassed bust of Theodosius I right, with the imperial titulature D N THEODO–SIVS P F AVG. It is likely from the mint of Cyzicus, Bithynia, probably one of the Æ3 ‘Concordia Auggg’ issues (AD 378–83).²⁶ This is suggested by some features found in many of the dies from the early Theodosian issues of Cyzicus, such as the small, narrow imperial bust with a proportionally larger head, the V–shaped drapery folds under the neck, as well as parallels in the graphic form of the obverse legend letters.

Similar numeral engravings also appear on the reverse of five late Roman *tesserae*. These are (die–)connected to the ‘Vota Publica’ token issue from the fourth century AD, which bear images of Roman emperors or Egyptian deities (Serapis, Isis, Hermanubis) on the obverse combined with reverse types portraying Egyptian and Isiac imagery, accompanied by the legend ‘Vota Publica’.²⁷ These tokens, made of either bronze or brass, consist of two major series:

- i.) the ‘imperial’ series, including an earlier small cluster by the mint of Carthage produced around the Second Tetrarchy (AD 305–06), and a later larger issue struck by the Roman mint from the reign of Constantine I (AD 313–330/31) through at least the first two generations of the Valentinian dynasty (AD 365–78);
- ii.) the ‘anonymous’ series, which displays the bust of Serapis, Isis, or Hermanubis (or the jugate busts of Serapis and Isis) on the obverse instead of imperial busts. This series has commonly been attributed to the Roman mint due to some die–links between a few ‘anonymous’ pieces and certain groups of the ‘imperial’ series from the Valentinian period.²⁸

The ‘Vota Publica’ pieces with numeral marks all come from the ‘anonymous’ series. They bear a radiate and bearded bust of Serapis on the obverse (accompanied by a variously spelled legend: DEO SE–RAPIDI, DEO SAR–APIDI, or even erroneously DEO SAR–ARIDI; Cat. nos 16–18, **Pl. 5, 16–18**), or a bust of Isis right wearing a *basileion* (obverse legend: ISIS F–ARIA; Cat. no. 19, **Pl. 5, 19**), or the jugate, draped busts of Serapis and Isis facing right (obverse legend: DEO SAR–APIDI; Cat. no. 20, **Pl. 5, 20**). Based on Bricault and Mondello’s recent catalogue, three of the specimens (Cat. nos 17–18, 20) are individually obverse die–linked to three ‘anonymous’ clusters with an internal die–linked structure, which show a variety of Egyptian types on the reverse.²⁹ The other two (Cat. nos 16, 19), on the other hand, cannot be associated with any of the known ‘anonymous’ clusters including die–linked pieces, as their obverse dies are not otherwise attested.³⁰ The dating of the ‘anonymous’ series is far from certain. Unlike previous literature that often attributed these pieces to the reign of Julian and his ‘pagan renaissance’ (AD 361–63), Alföldi

²⁵ Cf. *RIC* IX, Aquileia, nos 17D, 18C.

²⁶ *RIC* IX, Cyzicus, nos 16, 17C, 18C.

²⁷ Cf. Alföldi 1937; Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming).

²⁸ Alföldi 1937, pp. 16–18, 20, 22, 25–9.

²⁹ Cf. Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), nos S21.1, S50.1, S&I16.1, which are respectively die–linked with Group 2 (Part b), Group 14 (Part b), and Group 10 (Part b).

³⁰ Cf. Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), nos S164.1, I128.1, which have been respectively sorted into the following non–die linked ‘anonymous’ groups: Group 128 (Part c); Group 154 (Part c).

dated this issue to between AD 379–80 and 395 based on stylistic and historical clues.³¹ If so, these pieces may be the latest from the group of engraved coins and tesseræ presented in this paper, as their production would date to an unspecified time span within the reign of Theodosius I (AD 379–95).

Engraved Roman numerals and coherence of the group

The above analysis, accompanied by the information on the relevant Roman numeral occurring on the reverse of these specimens, is summarised in Table 1.

The specimens discussed are a heterogeneous group of mostly bronze coins and *tesseræ* which were initially part of official coin issues minted in Rome and the provinces at different times and places from the reigns of Nero to Theodosius. As shown in the catalogue below, the diameters of these pieces vary between *c.* 15 and 23mm, while their weight ranges from 0.75 to 9.04g. Unsurprisingly, the metrology of these pieces varies significantly as they were originally produced at different times during the long evolution of the Roman coin system which underwent numerous reforms to bronze coinage. All of these objects were then later ‘recycled’ with a new purpose by incising a large-sized Roman numeral on their reverses, which marked an additional stage in their life-cycle.

As Table 1 shows, Roman numerals run within a range from I to XVI in the available material. Some numbers (I, V, XI, XVI) are attested by only one piece, while others (III, IIII/IV, VIII, VIII/IX, XIII, XIII/II) by two or more specimens up to a maximum of four. The numerals II, VI, VII, X, XI, XII, and XV are not attested, but these gaps are probably the result of an incomplete survival of material to the present day. Only the reverse on no. 13 is an exception, as it shows two non-numeral graffiti on the reverse: a palm branch in the left field and a monogram formed by the ligature of the letters P and E in the right field. Notably, this monogram is not a hapax, since it is found – among other items – on the relatively contemporary contorniate medallions (alternatively occurring with the ligature PF here). Various resolved as *palma emerita*, *praemia emerita*, *palma feliciter*, or *praemiis feliciter remunerabimur*, particularly due to the image of a palm leaf/branch accompanying the PE letters in many instances, the meaning of this monogram has mostly been connected to the notion of victory, with reference to triumphant acclamations or agonistic and sporting competitions.³² As will be discussed below, this coin may have had a particular connotation within this cluster, or it could instead stand apart.

As the weight and diameter of these coins vary greatly, as well as their dating and issuing mint, the interlinkage of these specimens as part of a single group needs a closer look.

The analysis of the sample shows that, where determinable, the numeral engravings occurred on two Roman provincial coins from the Julio–Claudian and Flavian periods (Corinth and Alabanda respectively), twelve fourth-century Roman imperial coins from both eastern (Siscia, Cyzicus, Constantinople) and western mints (Rome,

³¹ Alföldi 1937, p. 25. A new and complete survey on the ‘anonymous’ series from the ‘Vota Publica’ token issue is currently being undertaken by L. Bricault and C. Mondello.

³² On the PE monogram cf. Bruzza 1877; Alföldi and Alföldi 1990, pp. 276–312; Mittag 1999, pp. 173–9; Garipzanov 2018, pp. 115–18.

Table 1. Coins and *tesserae* with engraved numerals on their reverses.

Specimen cat. no.	Original series	Reverse engraving
1	Æ, Corinth, Achaea (AD 66–7) (<i>RPC</i> I, 1204)	I
2	Æ, Alabanda, Caria (AD 69–79) (<i>RPC</i> II, 1203)	XIII
3	Æ, undetermined series, Rome or Ostia, reign of Maxentius (AD 308–311/12)	VIII
4	Æ, ‘Fel Temp Reparatio’ series, Constantinople (AD 348–51) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Constantinople, 81–2)	VIII
5	Æ, undetermined series and issuing mint, reign of Magnentius (AD 350–3)	XIII
6	Æ, ‘VOTA X – XX’ series, undetermined issuing mint, reign of Julian (AD 361–3)	III
7	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Constantinople (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Constantinople, 165–7) (?)	III
8	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MV•LT/XX’ series, Rome (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Rome, 328–30)	IV
9	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MV•LT/XX’ series, Rome (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Rome, 328–30)	VIII
10	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Siscia, 414–16, 420–2)	VIII
11	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Siscia, 414–16, 420–2)	XI
12	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Constantinople (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Constantinople, 165–7)	XIII
13	Æ, ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia (AD 361–3) (<i>RIC</i> VIII, Siscia, 414–16, 420–2)	Palm branch in l. field; PE monogram in r. field
14	Æ, ‘Gloria Romanorum’ or ‘Securitas Reipublicae’ series, Aquileia (AD 375–8) (<i>RIC</i> IX, Aquileia, 17D, 18C)	VIII
15	Æ, ‘Concordia Auggg’ series, Cyzicus (AD 378–83) (<i>RIC</i> IX, Cyzicus, 16, 17C, 18C)	XII
16	Brass, ‘Vota Publica’ tokens, ‘anonymous’ series, Rome (AD 379/80–395?)	III
17	Æ, ‘Vota Publica’ tokens, ‘anonymous’ series, Rome (AD 379/80–95?)	V
18	Æ, ‘Vota Publica’ tokens, ‘anonymous’ series, Rome (AD 379/80–95?)	XIII
19	Æ, ‘Vota Publica’ tokens, ‘anonymous’ series, Rome (AD 379/80–95?)	XIII
20	Æ, ‘Vota Publica’ tokens, ‘anonymous’ series, Rome (AD 379/80–95?)	XVI

Ostia [?], Aquileia), and five late Roman *tesserae* (Rome). This could lead to the conclusion that these specimens were incised at different times and for different purposes, rejecting the idea that they were part of a single set sharing the same type of mark. However, as seen from the available evidence on Greek and Roman coin circulation (mostly through coin finds and hoards), coins in antiquity often remained in circulation long after they were minted. In addition, in regards to Roman imperial and provincial coinage, ‘foreign’ coins (that is, struck in a given Roman city or province) could enter the monetary circulation of other Roman cities or provinces to improve local coin supply – especially when local production was scarce or in times of coin shortage –, thus exceeding the limits of their former local circulation context.³³ For instance, the continued use of older Roman coins to serve as currency, often in a different area than that of their original circulation, can be seen in the evidence provided by the legionary countermarks of the East (all of which belong to the period between the last years of Nero and the eastern expedition of Lucius Verus) or by the denominational marks which were applied in the eastern provinces by one city to its own coins or to coins of other cities, with examples up to after AD 250 (especially in Asia Minor).³⁴ A later example is the numeral countermarks XLII and LXXXIII that were either stamped or engraved on Roman bronze coins from the Principate (mostly Roman middle bronzes and sestertii of the first and second centuries AD, with a larger amount from the Flavian period). According to the traditional view, these marks were made in Vandal Africa as they would match some of the denominational values in *nummi* of the Vandal monetary system;³⁵ other proposals have instead related them to Ostrogothic Italy, mainly based on find-spot evidence of many of the coins.³⁶ Dated to the late fifth or early sixth centuries depending on views concerning their attribution, these marks prove that first and second century AD Roman coins had been brought back in circulation in the Vandal or Ostrogothic kingdom some 400 years after their initial issue – perhaps resulting from the discovery of a large hoard – by means of an *ad hoc* countermarking method.³⁷

It follows that variations in the issuing date and mint between the coins discussed here do not necessarily mean that the application of numeral marks was made individually, at different times and places. Ideally, a potentially conclusive factor in determining the relationship between similar engravings found on diverse coins (and *tesserae*) should be provided by dated evidence (such as hoards or coin finds from

³³ E.g., Howgego 2014. A similar phenomenon has also recently been seen in Roman bronze and orichalcum tokens, some of which occasionally travelled to regions other than their place of production, as shown by their recorded find-spots: Rowan 2023, pp. 199–212.

³⁴ Howgego 1985, pp. 17–37.

³⁵ Friedländer 1879; Wroth 1911, p. xviii; Morrisson 1983.

³⁶ Cf. Grierson and Blackburn 1986, pp. 28–31, who argued that these ‘countermarked’ Roman coins ‘formed a supplementary fractional coinage in Ostrogothic Italy and may have been used in Vandal Africa’.

³⁷ As is known, Roman coins were also occasionally reused in modern times. See, for instance, the peculiar case of a Hadrian’s *as* bearing a countermark commonly labelled as ‘G fleurdelisé’ on the reverse (dated c. 1803), which was intended to give legal tender to this coin as well as to 18th-century French coppers which were found in circulation in the early 19th century West Indies: cf. Jambu 2018, 469–70.

datable contexts) together with meaningful quantities of material. Unfortunately, none of the specimens discussed here come from known find-spots or archaeological contexts, and the amount of material available is scarce.

Despite the paucity of data and absence of recorded contexts, some clues suggest that these engraved coins and *tesserae* were part of the same ensemble. First of all, the Roman numerals in question arise from the same (rare) engraving technique, which consists of two steps: 1) expunction of the original type by smoothing the reverse surface of the piece; 2) engraving of a single large-sized Roman numeral in a rough style, by means of a burin or even a non-professional tool. Such a practice consisting of fully smoothing off the reverse of an older struck object to make a field for an incised number is almost completely unprecedented on coins, whereas it is found on some contorniate medallions, although infrequently and involving marks or symbols different from those examined here.³⁸

The original obverse type of the pieces, which shows the bust of either a Roman emperor or a deity, was also invariably retained without any alterations. Whatever the meaning of this choice, this meant that the visual features of these recycled objects, as the components of a new system/series, were created by the pairing of the portrait of a ruler or deity on the obverse with a Roman numeral on the reverse. These characteristics may also have helped distinguish these pieces from 'regular' coins.

A further argument for these incised Roman numerals being interconnected is the relative proximity of the production date of most specimens. Indeed, these engravings were meaningfully executed on pieces that were mostly minted in the fourth century AD, ranging from the reign of Maxentius to that of Theodosius, with a higher concentration of pieces from the second half of that century.

³⁸ To this author's knowledge, the engraving of a Roman numeral mark on coins via the above-technique is only documented by a single Roman provincial example, a coin of Nero struck at around AD 60 by the mint of Tralles, Lydia: Nomos, Obolos Web Auction 14, 15 December 2019, lot 351 (on its relevant coins series, see *RPC* I, no. 2656: <https://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/coins/1/2656>). Here the original reverse type (that is, a terminal statue of Athena Alkidemos r., holding a shield on left arm and wielding a spear, with the legend *KAIAPAION*) was erased and then replaced by the mark III • V running on three lines in incuse. In this author's opinion, this piece does not belong to the group presented in this paper due to the presence of a different numeral engraving pattern. The same applies to a bronze medallet (a small-sized contorniate imitation?), now in Paris (BnF, 17083: <https://catalogue.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/cb458773653>), which shows a helmeted and cuirassed bust of Rome (or Pallas?) r. on the obverse, while on the reverse is the Roman numeral XXVI engraved above a former erased motif that is no longer identifiable: see de Belfort 1892, p. 171, pl. VI.1. On contorniates, diversified motifs or symbols were occasionally applied to the reverse of the specimen after having erased and smoothed their original design (e.g., see Alföldi and Alföldi 1976, cat. no. 42, pl. 15.9 = Mondello 2019, p. 159, no. 21), but they more frequently appear to be engraved over the former types through various other techniques: cf. Alföldi and Alföldi 1990, 241–353; Mittag 1999, p. 172; Mondello 2019. With regard to ancient tokens, a number ranging from 1 to 15 is engraved, in both Greek and Latin numerals, on the reverse of some uniface bone and ivory 'tesserae', generally alongside a label (in Greek) referring to the obverse image: e.g., cf. Alföldi–Rosenbaum 1976; Bianchi 2015. Predominantly regarded as counters for a game which may have spread across the Empire from Egypt, these bone and ivory 'tesserae', however, differ greatly from the objects examined here in size, material, and typology. For some 'Vota Publica' token specimens, the obverse surface of which has been smoothed without applying any countermark or graffiti, see Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), nos E18.1, E111.1.

All these aspects together support the idea that the Roman numerals were applied at the same place and probably at approximately the same time, reusing official bronze coins (provincial and imperial) from different series, mints, and issuing periods which were available in the geographical area where they were engraved. Given that one third of this sample was a product of the Roman mint and the later pieces date back to the reign of Theodosius (AD 379–95), one might suppose that these materials were repurposed in the city of Rome or nearby, perhaps not too long after his reign, i.e. the late fourth or early fifth century AD.³⁹

Unfortunately, the absence of find or provenance data for any of these pieces prevents the determination of a precise chronology or geographical distribution for their engraving. Whether these pieces were incised all at once or on several occasions in small groups can also not be determined. However, this did most likely occur within a short period of time. Interestingly, a similar numeral incision appears engraved on the reverse of two Roman bronze *tabulae ansatae*. Of these, one is anepigraphic and undated, showing an erotic (homosexual?) scene on one side and the numeral II on the other; the other bears a pearl–diademed and draped bust of Honorius right on one side, accompanied by the legend HONOR–IVS P F AVG, and the numeral VIII on the other (Pl. 6, 27–8). For the latter *tabula*, the bust style, the imperial titulature, and the legend division echo the ‘Urbs Roma Felix’ series, which was struck almost entirely at Rome during the period of 404–08, with a hypothetical revival after Attalus.⁴⁰ In both bronze tablets, traces of an earlier image can be found on the side where the number was incised, as with the engraving technique seen on the coins discussed. While no factual connection can be posited between these *tabulae ansatae* and the focused coins due to their different typology, the similarities between these two categories of artefacts in terms of the numeral engraving pattern and its technique provide at least some parallels for this practice at the time of Honorius. The location of fresh material bearing this rare type of numeral mark may provide additional clues on this late antique phenomenon.

Affiliation of the numeral marks and their possible purpose

After positively assessing the coherence of this coin cluster, what meaning should be attributed to these artefacts? Did the numeral engravings refer to a new system designed in late antiquity or were they intended to connect to a scheme previously seen in Roman coinage? What were these recycled coins for? Even though our ensemble is a small sample and does not allow us to draw any definitive conclusions, some possible answers to these questions can be proposed by first exploring what these objects are not.

³⁹ Given the rarity of these marks and the small number of surviving pieces, it seems less likely that these specimens were repurposed within a long period of time or across multiple geographically distant areas, or were individually incised to serve separate functions. In earlier scholarship, Alföldi 1975, pp. 19–20, maintained already that some of the pieces examined here were part of the same ensemble, proposing that ‘ihre Umgestaltung zu Spielmarken erfolgte zweifellos in den Jahren um 400’.

⁴⁰ Kent 1988, pp. 282–4; RIC X, pp. 130–1, 140–1.

These particular items are different from Roman provincial coins which were countermarked with an ‘official’ imprint sanctioned by the state or a local authority, many of which, as shown by Howgego, were connected to the names or symbols of Roman legions based along the northern and eastern frontiers.⁴¹ Indeed, there are no similarities between the numbers incised on the fourth-century bronze coins and the so-called ‘Greek imperial countermarks’ in terms of shape, numerical value, or application technique. In fact, while the numbers discussed here are large-format marks individually hand-engraved after smoothing the reverse of the recycled coin, the countermarks on Roman provincial coins, many of which contain Latin or Greek numbers (sometimes combined with letters or even drawings), were serially stamped with a small die in various positions upon the original type (mostly on the obverse side), normally appearing within a small-format square (or ovoid) punch.⁴² This method best suited the needs of a mass-revalidation process of money supply by imprinting a countermark on host coins without additional alteration, in order to revalidate or redenominate the issues as legal tender in the cheapest and fastest way, probably mostly to serve for payment or donations to the troops. The same applies to the small-sized Vandal or Ostrogothic marks found on first and second centuries AD Roman coins, which were either punched or engraved in a crude style above the original design (either on the obverse or reverse side) mostly transversally oriented. Furthermore, the numerals XLII and LXXXIII documented on these marks, which may have referred to some of the denominations in *nummi* of the Vandal system, do not fit the numeral sequence found on the coins and *tesserae* discussed here.

The rough style of the numbers inscribed, the non-professional engraving technique, the reduced volume of recycled materials for this practice and their poor metal composition suggest that these marks were private, made by and for a small group of individuals (or possibly executed by craftsmen at private request) to serve non-public or non-official purposes. Notably, the full erasure of the original reverse type, which was an integral part of coins as currency, implies an underlying demonetisation in the secondary use of these materials. Moreover, this is also confirmed by the fact that the primary use of some of these specimens already technically conformed to that of ‘*tesserae*’ or ‘tokens’, which lacked any monetary roles *sensu stricto*.

Furthermore, a comparative examination of the pieces belonging to the assemblage shows that the Roman numerals have no actual connection either with the metrological features of the specimens or the portraits displayed on the obverses. With regards to the metrology, the varying weights and modules of the known examples sharing the same Roman numeral as well as, more generally, the lack of solid correspondences between the engravings and the chosen denominations seem to suggest randomised selection of coins for reuse. Unless one takes into account the unlikely idea that these cheap pieces made of poor metal were (re-)monetised or (re-)denominated based on predetermined and disparate trust values regardless of their individual intrinsic

⁴¹ Cf. Howgego 1985, p. 17 and *passim*.

⁴² Cf. Howgego 1985, pp. 249–57, nos 725–41 (legionary countermarks with Roman numerals), and pp. 259–93, nos 746–837 (denominational countermarks with Greek numerals).

value, these variations make it improbable that the marks were meant to fulfill some monetary or fiscal task, with the numbers being matched to a given denomination or sum of money. Similarly, the remarkable weight fluctuations between the pieces also allow us to exclude the possibility that the value of the numbers referred to corresponding *siliqua* weights, as clumsily argued by some in the numismatic trade.⁴³ Likewise, given the apparent subdivision into multiple units (= 1, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16) of the number sequence recorded by the engravings, it is unlikely that these pieces were used as *tesserae* for counting operations, since the latter generally involved sequential mathematical chains with limited gaps (e.g., 1, 2, 4, 8, 16; or 1, 5, 10, 15).⁴⁴

If we look at the obverse types, non-uniform criteria in pairing a portrait of a Roman emperor or deity on the obverse and a Roman numeral on the reverse can also be noticed. For instance, the same portrait has been connected to different numbers on these materials: this is the case with Julian, the most recurrent imperial bust, which is variously associated with III, IIII/IV, VIII, XIII/IX, and XIII. Correspondingly, the same Roman numeral is matched with more than one portrait. As for the most frequently attested numbers, VIII is found on four pieces showing an imperial portrait of Maxentius, Julian, or Valentinian II; XIII occurs on three pieces with a portrait of the Demos or Zeus, Julian, or Serapis. Hence, one can conclude that the Roman numeral engraved on the reverse was the real signifier within the new system to which the pieces were connected, while the portrait of emperor or deity on the obverse may have played a minor role or even had no real significance, merely arising from a random choice of reused material and kept as a decorative element.

The idea that these coins and coin-like objects were reused as legal tender or tokens connected with some particular fiscal service or counting operations can be discarded; the most likely solution in this author's opinion is that these items were converted into gaming pieces for an otherwise unattested Roman *ludus*. At least judging by the numerical values expressed by the incisions, the game plan in question had to include a structure involving a sequence ranging from I to XVI, against which the pieces were employed following certain rules. If so, these numbered *tesserae* may have been made from recycled material by a small group of private users (the players themselves?) to satisfy their recreational pleasures. They may have served as chips or other gaming pieces for some sort of board game or played on the *tabulae lusoriae*, which were engraved on the floor of *fora*, roads, markets, *tabernae*, or other contexts. Furthermore, if piece no. 13, showing a palm branch and the PE monogram on the reverse, is indeed to be connected to this group, it is tempting to assume that it had a separate task (a sort of winner's gaming token?): this is suggested by its different appearance compared to the other average gaming pieces which had a Roman numeral, as well as the possible correlation of its two graffiti

⁴³ On the piece labelled here as no. 11, see for instance the *VCoins. The Online Coin Show* website, Seller: London Ancient Coins, Ltd., SKU: 11937 (<https://www.vcoins.com/en/Default.aspx>).

⁴⁴ Thus Martini 1997, pp. 10–11, who made this point with regards to the numbers figured on the reverse of the so-called *spintriae*.

to the notion of victory or the prize for the winner.⁴⁵ Alternatively, it could part of another group made from recycled bronze small change. It is worth mentioning that a ludic function was already contemplated by Andreas Alföldi with regards to some – but not all – of the pieces from this ensemble he was able to examine in his day. However, the religious implications he speculated about in relation to these objects as ‘heathen’ equivalents to some early fifth-century bronze Christian *tesserae* not only lacks evidence, but are dismissed by the remarkably different morphology and pictorial spectrum of the latter.⁴⁶

Interestingly, the number sequence I–XVI is attested on the reverse of the best-known bronze and orichalcum tokens from the Julio–Claudian period, the obverse imagery of which displays imperial busts, *symplegmata* or erotic scenes (the so-called ‘*spintriae*’), and varia (deity portraits and diversified figures, playful or religious scenes, imperial symbols etc.). On these *tesserae*, the numbers are depicted on the reverse generally within a dotted border and wreath, and range from I to XVI, sometimes bearing the additional letter A or even AVG (Pl. 6, 29–30).⁴⁷ Despite an impressive amount of research, no consensus has been reached on the function of these token groups from the High Empire, the meaning of their Roman numerals, and the nature of their mutual relationship.⁴⁸ Mostly regarded as part of a single series minted at the mint of Rome, these token clusters have been variously held as admission tickets, brothel tokens, or as devices for military donatives or private imperial *congiaria*;⁴⁹ depending on the hypothesis supported, the value of the Roman numerals has been referred to a sum of money expressed in *asses*, the number of Roman legions from the late Augustan period, or, though less likely, corresponding holes in the abacus for counting. A gaming function has instead been posited for these tokens by Mowat and others, which may have served as a set of (board?) game

⁴⁵ A more modern comparandum of a special gaming ‘token’ can be seen in the ‘Joker’ playing card which is found in modern French, Italian, and Spanish card games. On the understanding of this token as a ‘Zeichen des Gewinners der Partie’, see also Alföldi 1975, p. 20.

⁴⁶ Alföldi 1975, p. 20. Moreover, Alföldi’s idea that these pieces were used as gaming pieces by ‘pagans’ against the backdrop of a ‘pagan reaction’ does not explain why they also included some bronze coins representing Christian rulers (Constantius II, Valentinian II, Theodosius I) on the obverse. On the possible function of the above-mentioned early fifth century Christian bronze *tesserae* as liturgical or community devices see Mondello 2021, pp. 148–51.

⁴⁷ Other tokens with a range up to XXV, known through unique or rare specimens, differ in style and depictions from the *spintriae* and other Julio–Claudian tokens, and have accordingly been considered of a later date or spurious: e.g., see Buttrey 1973, pp. 52–3; Simonetta and Riva 1981, p. 6; Martini 1997, p. 5; Campana 2009, p. 54.

⁴⁸ As for the relation between these groups, scholarship has identified die-matches between the tokens with imperial busts, the *spintriae*, the ‘Mora’ tokens, and the token series of Gaius Mitreius, *magister iuventutis*: cf. Buttrey 1973, pp. 56–7; Martínez Chico 2018, pp. 545–6; Rowan 2020, pp. 107–8. On the dating of these tokens, ranging from the reign of Tiberius to the time of Claudius (or, less likely, to the reign of Domitian), see Martini 1999, p. 13; Campana 2009, p. 54; Küter 2019, p. 91.

⁴⁹ Admission tickets: Spanheim 1664, p. 285; Eckhel 1798, p. 315; Cohen 1859, p. XXII; Lenormant 1878–1879, p. 63; Stevenson 1889, pp. 758–9. Brothel tokens: Friedländer 1886; Nadrowski 1906, p. 287; Simonetta and Riva 1981. Devices for military donatives or private imperial *congiaria*: Martini 1997, pp. 13–14.

pieces not otherwise known⁵⁰ or as devices in other types of gaming and lotteries, with the different numbers referring to different types of prizes in a randomised distribution system.⁵¹

It is notable that the bronze coins discussed here are closely reminiscent of many of the features of the bronze and brass *tesserae* from the Julio–Claudian period, particularly those bearing an imperial portrait. Both of these groups share some common elements, such as: the representation of the effigy of a Roman emperor on the obverse (or, alternatively, of a bust of a deity on the repurposed coins); the depiction of a large-sized Roman numeral on the reverse, following a number sequence ranging from I to XVI; and the use (or re-use) of pieces made of poor intrinsic value metal (bronze or brass), with an Æ3 or Æ4 module, to produce series aimed at serving a non-monetary function.

Some hints may be drawn from such similarities, which should however be considered with some caution. If the fourth-century coins provided with a numeral mark actually evoke the Julio–Claudian tokens with an imperial portrait, instead of being part of a new system with its own meaning, the former may have been repurposed as rough imitations of the latter in late antiquity.⁵² If so, it would follow that these late Roman objects were repurposed to fulfill the same function served by the tokens with an imperial effigy from the Principate. The proposed ludic purpose of the engraved coins would accordingly give further support to a position taken by some scholars on the Julio–Claudian tokens which argues that they are gaming pieces as well. Moreover, it is noteworthy that the later numeral engravings were possibly also executed in Rome, the same area where the bronze and brass tokens and *spintriae* from the early first century may have been struck.⁵³

Although this assumption is tempting, such a connection between the Julio–Claudian tokens and the fourth-century engraved coins remains uncertain (at least for the moment); further evidence, e.g. the discovery of specimens in a secure context from both these categories of artefacts, is needed for a more certain conclusion.⁵⁴ The potential conversion of these fourth century bronze coins and *tesserae*, against the

⁵⁰ Mowat 1898, p. 21; Buttrey 1973, p. 54 ('the tokens may have served as counters in gaming, the numbers corresponding to moves or positions, or to points wagered or gained'); Bateson 1991; Benassi and Giordani and Poggi 2003, pp. 259–62; Campana 2009, pp. 55–6; Duggan 2017; Martínez Chico 2018; Küter 2019, pp. 90, 93.

⁵¹ Thus Rowan 2020, pp. 101, and 108, who has also regarded the die-matched tokens from the Julio–Claudian period as part of separate issues from the same workshop rather than as belonging to a single coherent series.

⁵² This possibility has briefly been contemplated but not discussed by Küter 2019, 79, fns. 8–9, regarding the coin labelled here as no. 1, as well as the following example (not found by this author): Roma Numismatics, E–Sale 3, 2 November 2013, lot 526.

⁵³ For the issuing mint of the Julio–Claudian tokens to be identified as Rome, see e.g.: Martini 1999, p. 13; Campana 2009, p. 54; Küter 2019, p. 79; Rowan 2020, p. 109.

⁵⁴ However, it should be noted that the latest discovery context of the *spintriae* and tokens from the Julio–Claudian period that has been recorded so far dates to the beginning of Nero's reign at the latest (i.e., the 2003 finding of an imitative gilded *spintria* from a tomb in Mutina: cf. Benassi and Giordani and Poggi 2003) and no evidence is available (for the time being) on the possibility that these *tesserae* continued to circulate from the Flavian period onwards. For an up-to-date overview of the recorded find-spots of *spintriae* and, more generally, Roman tokens, cf. Rowan 2023, pp. 199–212.

backdrop of a (ludic?) private setting, would not only have important implications for our understanding of bronze and brass tokens in the High Empire, but would also indicate that this type of object was still known almost three centuries after they were first issued and remained in demand into late antiquity.

A noteworthy feature of some of these later coins is that they were pierced. Ten or eleven of the pieces recorded here have holes that exposed one side of the flan (Cat. nos 1 [?], 3–6, 8–9, 11, 13, 18–19). The ratio between the position of the hole and the coin axis shows that at least some were pierced after being incised. Indeed, the drilled hole displayed the side showing the Roman numeral in some examples (Cat. nos 4 [?], 9, 18) and affected the area of the numeral incision in others (Cat. nos 6, 19), indicating that this piercing was done subsequent to the engraving.⁵⁵ Numerous examples from ancient coinage show that this type of coin intervention was mostly aimed at binding the modified materials by perishable laces or *funicula* as ornamental components of jewelry to be worn on the neck, wrist, or even feet.⁵⁶ Being widely popular in the Roman world since the third century AD, coin set jewelry continued to be appreciated in late antiquity when new types were introduced and artefacts were created that combined exceptional artistic quality and considerable economic value.⁵⁷ The most elaborate inserted coins – usually gold – into pendants, rings, bracelets, brooches, belts, and body-chains. Other less valuable jewelry was also created with bronze coins. In other cases, the piercing of bronze or other coins of less precious metal converted them into votives or charms with an apotropaic value (e.g., to ward off evil spirits or illness), especially where their imagery evoked connections to magic and folk religion and could thus be invested with new religious and cultural meanings.⁵⁸

On the whole, the interventions and/or alterations carried out on these items allow us to gain an insight into their complex and multifaceted history. After their manufacture, these objects were transformed into numbered *tesserae*, probably to serve as gaming pieces in late fourth or early fifth century Rome; at some unspecified later date (late Roman period or later?) they moved to a third different phase of their life cycle, where they were holed for suspension to serve as ornamental jewels or possibly as amulets. The history of these objects reveals that they were multifunctional objects which attained new meanings through appropriate adjustments and changes. This case-study also provides further insight into the extent to which coins (and coin-like objects) could exceed their original strictly monetary use and be adapted to fulfil the needs or desires in new contexts arising from the broader social-economic and cultural dynamics of Roman society.

⁵⁵ These features resulting from the piercing, along with the fact that some of the coins were holed to expose the obverse portrait (Cat. nos 3, 5, 8) thus hiding their reverse Roman numeral, seem to suggest that the piercing relates to a different and later phase than the engraving in the life of these objects, making it unlikely that it was somehow connected with the repurposing of the coins as gaming tokens.

⁵⁶ Cf. Morrisson 1980; Callu 1991; Bursche 2008; Perassi 2005; Morelli 2009; Manfredi 2011; Perassi 2011; Perassi 2021a.

⁵⁷ Perassi 2021b.

⁵⁸ E.g., see Fulghum 2001.

Conclusions

Based on the above analysis, the Roman numerals incised on the bronze coins and *tesserae* discussed here were intended to turn these pieces into gaming tokens. The numeral engravings occurring on the reverse of the specimens, connected to their original obverse types showing the portrait of an emperor or a deity, appear to have had a particular value or played a given task within a Roman game, the details of which are now lost. Comparative examination of the original issuing dates and mints of the coins and *tesserae* suggests that the application of these numeral marks may have been carried out in the city of Rome or its vicinity in the late fourth or early fifth century AD. Moreover, affinities with some of the numeral *tesserae* from the Julio–Claudian period, which bear an imperial portrait on the obverse and a Roman numeral on the reverse, might suggest that the bronze coins were private imitations of these made in late antiquity. The present state of our evidence prevents firmer conclusions, but additional insight might be possible through future developments in numismatic and archaeological research.

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Catalogue

All specimens are illustrated on **Plates 4–6**.

1. Æ (Ø 20mm, 6.84g), Corinth, Achaia, AD 66–7.
Obv.: [NERO CAE(SAR) AVG IMP], Radiate head of Nero right.
Rev.: Notch or Roman numeral I incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Numismatik Lanz München 105, 26 November 2001, lot 477; Naville Numismatics 44, 4 November 2018, lot 119; *RPC* I, no. 1204.34 (included as an additional coin in *RPC* I’s online version after its printed edition; see: <https://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/coin/452267>)
2. Æ (Ø 21mm, 9.04g, 6h), Alabanda, Caria, AD 69–79. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304924 (Hess Nachfolger coll.).
Obv.: ΑΛΑΒΑΝΔΕΩΝ, head of the Demos or Zeus, bearded, right.
Rev.: Roman numeral XIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 6, pl. 7.6.

3. Æ (Ø 23mm, 4.88g, 2h), undetermined series, Rome or Ostia, AD 308–11/12.
Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304922 (von Quast coll.). Pierced at about 12 o'clock.
Obv.: IMP C MAXENTIVS P F AVG, Laureate head of Maxentius right.
Rev.: Roman numeral VIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 20, pl. 7.9.
4. Æ (Ø 22mm, 4.02g, 6h), 'Fel Temp Reparatio' series, Constantinople, AD 348–51.
Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304923 (von Quast coll.). Pierced at about 7 o'clock.
Obv.: D N CONSTAN-TIVS P F AVG, Pearl-diademed, draped, and cuirassed bust of Constantius II right, wearing a *paludamentum*.
Rev.: Roman numeral VIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 20, pl. 7.10.
5. Æ (no data recorded), undetermined series and issuing mint, AD 350–3. Once in A. de Belfort's collection. Pierced at about 12 o'clock.
Obv.: [D N] MAGNEN-TIVS P F AVG, Bareheaded, draped, and cuirassed bust of Magnentius right; A behind bust.
Rev.: Roman numeral XIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: de Belfort 1892, p. 130, pl. V.4.
6. Æ (Ø 18mm, 1.20g, 12h), 'VOTA X-XX' series, undetermined issuing mint, AD 361–3. British Museum, 1936,1212.1 (J.W.E. Pearce's donation). Pierced on right side at about 3 o'clock.
Obv.: (Worn legend), Diademed, helmeted, draped, and cuirassed bust of Julian left.
Rev.: Roman numeral III incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: –
7. Æ (Ø 17mm, 2.92g, 11h), 'VOT/X/MVLT/XX' series, Constantinople (?), AD 361–3. BnF, 17077.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI-ANVS P F AVG, Pearl-diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian left, holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Roman numeral IIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 2, pl. 7.2.
8. Æ (Ø 18mm, 2.43g, 3h), 'VOT/X/MV•LT/XX' series, Rome, AD 361–3. BnF, 17078. Pierced at about 12 o'clock.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI-ANVS P F AVG, Pearl-diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian left, holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Roman numeral IV incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 1, pl. 7.1.
9. Æ (Ø 19mm, 2.98g, 3h), 'VOT/X/MV•LT/XX' series, Rome, AD 361–3. BnF, 17080. Pierced at about 2 o'clock.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI-ANVS P F AVG, Pearl-diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian left, holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Roman numeral VIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 3, pl. 7.3.

10. Æ (Ø 20mm, 2.50g, 9h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia, AD 361–3. Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, RÖ 32684.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI–ANVS P F AVG, Pearl–diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian left, holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Roman numeral VIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: –
11. Æ (Ø 19mm, 3.00g), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia, AD 361–3. Private collection. Pierced at about 3 o’clock.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI–ANVS P F AVG, Pearl–diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian l., holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Roman numeral XI incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: –
12. Æ (Ø 20mm, 2.83g, 2h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Constantinople, AD 361–3. BnF, 17079.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI–ANVS P F AVG, Pearl–diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian left, holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Roman numeral XIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: de Belfort 1892, p. 130, pl. V.2; Alföldi 1964, pl. 1.9; Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 5, pl. 7.5; Mondello 2021, p. 131, pl. 27.5.
13. Æ (Ø 20mm, 2.87g, 12h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia, AD 361–3. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304921 (Martinetti coll.). Pierced at about 6 o’clock.
Obv.: D N FL CL IVLI–ANVS P F AVG, Pearl–diademed, helmeted, and cuirassed bust of Julian left, holding a spear in right hand and a shield over his l. shoulder, seen from behind.
Rev.: Smoothed surface engraved with a palm branch in left field, a PE monogram in right field.
References: Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 9, pl. 7.8.
14. Æ (Ø 17mm, 1.40g, 7h), ‘Gloria Romanorum’ or ‘Securitas Reipublicae’ series, Aquileia, AD 375–8. British Museum, 1936,1212.2 (J.W.E. Pearce’s donation).
Obv.: D N VALENTINIA–NVS IVN P F AVG, Youthful, pearl–diademed, and cuirassed bust of Valentinian II right, wearing a *paludamentum*.
Rev.: Roman numeral VIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: –
15. Æ (Ø 18mm, 2.14g, 12h), ‘Concordia Auggg’ series, Cyzicus, AD 378–83. BnF, 17081.
Obv.: D N THEODO–SIVS P F AVG, Pearl–diademed, draped, and cuirassed bust of Theodosius I right.
Rev.: Roman numeral XII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: de Belfort 1892, p. 131, pl. V.5; Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 10, pl. 7.11; Mondello 2021, p. 131, pl. 27.6.

16. Brass ‘Vota Publica’ token (0.75g), Rome, AD 379/80–395 (?). Turin, Museo di Antichità, F10384.
Obv.: DEO SE–RAPIDI, Radiate, draped, and bearded bust of Serapis right, wearing a modius.
Rev.: Roman numeral III incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), no. S164.1.
17. Æ ‘Vota Publica’ token (no data recorded), Rome, AD 379/80–395 (?).
Obv.: DEO SAR–APIDI, Radiate, draped, and bearded bust of Serapis right, wearing a modius.
Rev.: Roman numeral V incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Rollin and Feuardent, 02–11/05/1898, no. 2168 (Hoffmann coll.); Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 4, pl. 7.4; Göbl 1978, pl. XIX, no. 196; Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), no. S21.1.
18. Æ ‘Vota Publica’ token (Ø 17mm, 2.98g, 3h), Rome, AD 379/80–395 (?). Lausanne, Musée Cantonal d’Archéologie et d’Histoire (MCAH), MMC7807. Pierced at 8 o’clock.
Obv.: DEO SAR–ARIDI (*sic*), Radiate, draped, and bearded bust of Serapis right, wearing a modius.
Rev.: Roman numeral XIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), no. S50.1.
19. Æ ‘Vota Publica’ token (Ø 19mm, 3.06g, 12h), Rome, AD 379/80–95 (?). Basel, Historisches Museum, 1903.5984. Pierced at 9 o’clock.
Obv.: ISIS F–ARIA, Draped bust of Isis right, wearing a basileion.
Rev.: Roman numeral XIII incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: Alföldi 1937, no. 317, pl. IX, 25; Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), no. I128.1.
20. Æ ‘Vota Publica’ token (Ø 18mm, 2.75g), Rome, AD 379/80–95 (?).
Obv.: DEO SAR–APIDI, Jugate, draped busts right of Serapis, bearded and wearing a modius, and Isis, wearing a basileion.
Rev.: Roman numeral XVI incised into a flattened and erased surface.
References: de Belfort 1892 p. 130, pl. V, 3 (Fröhner coll.); Glendining, 16–21/11/1950, no. 2120 (Platt Hall coll.); Alföldi 1975, p. 19, no. 8, pl. 7.7; Göbl 1978, pl. XIX, no. 195; Sternberg XXXIII, 18–19 September 1997, lot 393; NAC 92, 23–24 May 2016, lot 781; Bricault and Mondello (forthcoming), no. S&I16.1.

Key to Plates 4–6

1. Æ (Ø 20mm, 6.84g), Corinth, Achaea, AD 66–7. © Numismatik Lanz München (<http://www.numislanz.de/>). (1.5x)
2. Æ (Ø 21mm, 9.04g, 6h), Alabanda, Caria, AD 69–79. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304924. © Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen. (1.5x)
3. Æ (Ø 21mm, 9.04g, 6h), Rome or Ostia, AD 308–311/312. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304922. © Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen. (1.5x)

4. *Æ* (Ø 22mm, 4.02g, 6h), “Fel Temp Reparatio” series, Constantinople, AD 348–351. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304923. © Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen. (1.5x)
5. *Æ* (no data recorded), undetermined series and issuing mint, AD 350–53. Source: © *Annuaire de la Société Française de Numismatique*. Not to scale.
6. *Æ* (Ø 18mm, 1.20g, 12h), ‘VOTA X–XX’ series, undetermined issuing mint, AD 361–3. British Museum, 1936,1212.1. © The Trustees of the British Museum. (1.5x)
7. *Æ* (Ø 17mm, 2.92g, 11h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Constantinople (?), AD 361–3. BnF, 17077. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
8. *Æ* (Ø 18mm, 2.43g, 3h), ‘VOT/X/MV•LT/XX’ series, Rome, AD 361–3. BnF, 17078. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
9. *Æ* (Ø 19mm, 2.98g, 3h), ‘VOT/X/MV•LT/XX’ series, Rome, AD 361–3. BnF, 17080. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
10. *Æ* (Ø 20mm, 2.50g, 9h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia (AD 361–3). Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, RÖ 32684. © Kunsthistorisches Museum, Vienna. (1.5x)
11. *Æ* (Ø 19mm, 3.00g), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia (AD 361–3). Private collection. (1.5x)
12. *Æ* (Ø 20mm, 2.83g, 2h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Constantinople, AD 361–3. BnF, 17079. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
13. *Æ* (Ø 20mm, 2.87g, 12h), ‘VOT/X/MVLT/XX’ series, Siscia (AD 361–3). Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18304921. © Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen. (1.5x)
14. *Æ* (Ø 17mm, 1.40g, 7h), ‘Gloria Romanorum’ or ‘Securitas Reipublicae’ series, Aquileia, AD 375–8. British Museum, 1936,1212.2. © The Trustees of the British Museum. (1.5x)
15. *Æ* (Ø 18mm, 2.14g, 12h), ‘Concordia Auggg’ series, Cyzicus, AD 378–83. BnF, 17081. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
16. Brass ‘Vota Publica’ token (0.75g), Rome, AD 379/380–395 (?). Museo di Antichità of Turin, F10384. © Museo di Antichità, Turin. Not to scale.
17. *Æ* ‘Vota Publica’ token (no data recorded), Rome, AD 379/380–395 (?). Source: © Rollin & Feuarent 1898. Not to scale.
18. *Æ* ‘Vota Publica’ token (Ø 17mm, 2.98g, 3h), Rome, AD 379/380–95 (?). MCAH, MMC7807. © Musée Cantonal d’Archéologie et d’Histoire (MCAH), Lausanne. (1.5x)
19. *Æ* ‘Vota Publica’ token (Ø 19mm, 3.06g, 12h), Rome, AD 379/380–95 (?). Basel, Historisches Museum, 1903.5984. © Historisches Museum, Basel. (1.5x)
20. *Æ* ‘Vota Publica’ token (Ø 18mm, 2.75g), Rome, AD 379/380–95 (?). © Numismatica Ars Classica NAC AG (<https://www.arsclassicacoins.com/>). (1.5x)
21. *Æ* (Ø 20mm, 7.45g), Corinth, Achaea, AD 66–7, reign of Nero (AD 54–68). Lanz 105, 26 November 2001, lot 470 (= *RPC* I, no. 1204.33) © Numismatik Lanz München (<http://www.numislanz.de/>) (1.5x)
22. *Æ* (Ø 20mm, 7.90g, 12h), Alabanda, Caria, reign of Vespasian (AD 69–79) (= *RPC* II, no. 1203.1). British Museum, *BMC* 19. © The Trustees of the British Museum. (1.5x)
23. *Æ* (Ø 24mm, 5.17g, 6h), Constantinople, reign of Constantius II (AD 348–51) = *RIC* VIII, Constantinople, 81). Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, RÖ 62768. © Kunsthistorisches Museum, Vienna. (1.5x)
24. *Æ* (Ø 18mm, 2.26g, 6h), Rome, reign of Julian (AD 361–3) (= *RIC* VIII, Rome, 329). ANS, 1944.100.21009. © American Numismatic Society, New York. (1.5x)

25. Æ (2.84g, 6h), Siscia, reign of Julian (AD 361–3) (= *RIC* VIII, Siscia, 415). Graz University, 2541. © Graz University. (1.5x)
26. Æ (Ø 17.5mm, 1.76g, 6h), Aquileia, reign of Valentinian II (AD 375–8) (= *RIC* IX, Aquileia, 18C). ANS, 1995.39.36. © American Numismatic Society, New York. (1.5x)
27. Æ *tabula ansata* (Ø 21x9mm, 1.88g, 12h), Rome (?), Roman imperial period. BnF, 17116. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
28. Æ *tabula ansata* (Ø 22x15mm, 2.23g, 12h), Rome (?), reign of Honorius (AD 404–08?). BnF, 17081A. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
29. Æ token, (Ø 21mm, 4.31g, 4h), Rome, Julio–Claudian period. BnF, 16982. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)
30. Æ token, (Ø 20mm, 5.44g, 7h), Rome, Julio–Claudian period. BnF, 16998. © Bibliothèque nationale de France, Paris. (1.5x)

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PLATE 4
(All 1.5x)

MONDELLO, *DISJECTA MEMBRA*. ENGRAVINGS WITH NUMERALS ON ROMAN BRONZE COINS AND *TESSERAE* FROM THE 4TH CENTURY AD (1)

PLATE 5
(All 1.5x)

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MONDELLO, *DISJECTA MEMBRA*. ENGRAVINGS WITH NUMERALS ON ROMAN BRONZE COINS AND TESSERAE FROM THE 4TH CENTURY AD (2)

PLATE 6
(All 1.5x)

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MONDELLO, *DISJECTA MEMBRA*. ENGRAVINGS WITH NUMERALS ON ROMAN BRONZE COINS
AND *TESSERAE* FROM THE 4TH CENTURY AD (3)

